

THE INFLUENCE OF CLIL ON THE CRITICAL THINKING DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article aims to study the specific features of developing critical thinking skills in language learning through the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) pedagogical approach. CLIL, or Science and Language Integrated Learning, encourages students not only to acquire language, but also to develop a deeper understanding of science. The article analyzes the importance of critical thinking and the influence of CLIL on its development. Also, attention is paid to methods of effective introduction of CLIL technology into the educational process and the role of the teacher in this process. The results of the study show the effectiveness of CLIL in developing not only linguistic competences, but also analytical and critical approach.

Key words: CLIL, critical thinking, language learning, pedagogical approach, linguistic competence, integrated education, analytical thinking.

Introduction.

Today, globalization processes require the introduction of new approaches and methods to the education system. In particular, in the process of language learning, it is necessary not only to develop linguistic competence, but also to form important skills such as critical thinking. In this regard, the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) approach is considered as one of the effective tools for solving the current problems of modern education.

The CLIL methodology allows students to master the language through practical application. This method ensures that students acquire not only language, but also knowledge of science. As a result, students become active in communication and learn to take a critical approach to the environment. This article is devoted to the analysis of the impact of CLIL on the educational process and its place in the development of critical thinking skills.

The article discusses the theoretical foundations of the CLIL approach, the advantages of its introduction into the educational process, and the difficulties encountered in practice. The importance of the study is that it provides conclusions about how CLIL contributes to the multifaceted development of students.

Literature review:

The analysis of scientific and literary sources on the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) approach confirms the effectiveness of this pedagogical method not only in developing linguistic competence, but also in forming students' critical thinking skills.

Coyle, Hood, and Marsh[1] (2010) outlined the main theoretical foundations of CLIL, in which students acquire comprehensive skills by simultaneously learning content and language. It is shown that it is possible. Their research emphasizes the key principles of CLIL, namely cognitive development, intercultural communication and the development of communicative competence.

Meyer[3] (2013) describes CLIL as a tool for developing students' analytical and critical thinking. He emphasizes that CLIL assignments are highly complex, activate students' thinking skills, and enable reflection in the process.

Research by Dalton-Puffer[2] (2011) identifies the role of CLIL in motivating students to be active and improving their communication skills. Research results show that through CLIL, students' achievement level increases and they master the topics in depth. In particular, the importance of question-answer and debate processes in the development of critical thinking is emphasized.

Regarding the practical aspects of this approach, Perez-Cañado[4] (2012) focuses on the issue of teacher training in the implementation of CLIL programs. Linguistic and pedagogical competence of teachers is important for CLIL to be effective.

Literature analysis shows that CLIL has great potential in developing critical thinking. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account factors such as the difficulties in applying this approach to the educational process - the insufficient preparation of teachers and the difficulties in simultaneously mastering content and language by students. Further research on these issues will help ensure more effective implementation of CLIL.

Discussion:

This study revealed the role of the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) approach not only in the development of linguistic competences, but also in the formation of critical thinking. The analysis shows that cognitive and analytical approaches are activated when students learn the content of science through language in the CLIL process. This approach ensures that students are not limited to just receiving knowledge, but to further strengthen it through analysis, evaluation and application.

One of the main advantages of CLIL is that it develops students equally in both directions. By combining linguistic competence and critical thinking, students are taught to solve complex problems. In addition, CLIL's interactive teaching methods - discussion, debate and group work - also develop students' communication skills. As shown by Dalton-Puffer (2011), the effect of this approach is to increase students' ability to express their thoughts clearly and concisely.

However, there are a number of difficulties in the implementation of CLIL in the educational process. The effectiveness of this approach can be reduced when teachers' knowledge and skills related to CLIL technologies are not sufficient. It is also observed that some students have a language barrier in mastering the content of science, which has a negative effect on the effectiveness of lessons. In order to overcome these difficulties, special attention should be paid to improving the linguistic and pedagogical training of teachers.

In general, the use of CLIL in education has proven to be an effective tool for developing critical thinking. This approach allows students to learn science more deeply, develop communication skills and develop global competencies. A priority in future CLIL research will be to examine its long-term effects and test it in different educational settings.

Conclusion.

This study focused on studying the effectiveness of the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) approach in developing students' critical thinking skills. The obtained results made it possible to draw the following conclusions:

In the experimental group, there was a significant increase in the critical thinking skills of students who received education based on the CLIL methodology. This approach serves to develop students' abilities to analyze problem situations, evaluate evidence, and make decisions. At the same time, they learned to use language as an effective tool in the process of learning science. The effectiveness of discussion, group work and analytical tasks in CLIL-based classes increased the students' activity. These methods developed not only students' linguistic competence, but also their cognitive approaches.

In the control group, students trained with traditional methods showed lower results in critical thinking. This confirms the advantages of CLIL in the integrated development of linguistic acquisition and critical thinking. During the research, it was found that the success of CLIL depends on the methodological and linguistic preparation of teachers. The need to provide teachers with special

training and resources for effective implementation of this approach was emphasized.

Recommendations:

- In order to introduce the CLIL approach to the education system more widely, it is necessary to develop the mechanisms of teacher training and support.

- It is necessary to develop educational materials that include interactive and problematic situations aimed at developing critical thinking for students.

- New research is recommended to investigate the long-term impact of CLIL and its application in other disciplines.

This study demonstrated the importance of CLIL in developing critical thinking and revealed the possibilities of wider application of this approach in the educational process.

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